

Adiabatic Discrete Ratchet Effect of a Rotor in the N -well Potential of Hindered Rotation

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We consider the azimuthal hopping motion of a polar rotor with a dipole moment μ in a periodic N -well potential of hindered rotation under the influence of adiabatic symmetric dichotomous fluctuations of an external electric field $\pm E$ with a period τ . A general expression is obtained for the average angular velocity Ω of unidirectional discrete rotation as a function of the direction φ_E of the applied field and the ratio $\varepsilon = \mu E/k_B T$ of the energy of the rotor-electric field interaction to thermal energy. The analysis of the symmetry of the obtained expression shows that the ratchet effect is absent for odd N , as well as for field orientations $\varphi_E = 0, \pi/N$, which coincide with the axes of potential wells and barriers with even N 's. With quadratic accuracy in $\varepsilon \ll 1$, there is also no ratchet effect for $N > 2$. If N is even and $\varphi_E = \pi/(2N)$, the absolute value of the average angular velocity is proportional to ε^N at $\varepsilon \ll 1$ and tends to $2\pi/\tau$ at $\varepsilon/N^2 \gg 1$. Graphical dependencies $(\tau/2\pi)\Omega(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)$ are represented for $N = 2, 4, 6, 8$.

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1. Introduction

At the microscale, a rotor is usually understood as a fragment of a molecule that can rotate around a chemical bond, which connects it either with another fragment of the molecule [1] or with atoms of the solid substrate [2]. Light-controlled unidirectional rotation of molecular rotors [3] is one of the types of molecular motors whose practical potential has received the highest international recognition: The 2016 Nobel Prize in Chemistry was awarded to J. P. Sauvage, J. F. Stoddart, and B. L. Feringa “for the development and production of molecular machines” [4]. The transformation of the unidirectional rotation into the directed translational motion was demonstrated in Ref. [5] by the example of an electrically driven four-wheeled molecule moving along a metal surface.

The phenomenon of the emergence of a directed motion in asymmetric systems in the absence of average applied forces under the influence of nonequilibrium fluctuations (the ratchet effect) was explained within the framework of the theory of Brownian motors or ratchets [6, 7]. For rotors, the development of this theory was based on a low-temperature kinetic approach, within which the motion of a particle in a periodic N -well potential relief is interpreted through a hopping mechanism of overcoming potential barriers [8]. It was shown that if the azimuthal motion of a rotor with a dipole moment μ occurs in an N -well potential of hindered rotation under the influence of an alternating electric field $E(t) = E_0 \cos \omega t$ (E_0 and ω are the amplitude and frequency of the field change with time t), then, in the second order of perturbation theory in a small electric field ($\varepsilon = \mu E_0/k_B T \ll 1$, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature), the ratchet effect occurs only at $N = 2$ and at orientations of the field vector different from the orientations of the axes of potential wells and barriers [8]. Numerical

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calculations free of approximation $\varepsilon \ll 1$ showed that the ratchet effect can also be observed at the even values of N [9].

In this article, we consider the adiabatic discrete ratchet effect of a polar rotor in an N -well potential of hindered rotation under the influence of dichotomous fluctuations of an external electric field. Obtaining analytical relations for the average velocity of the rotor directional rotation is possible due to the fact that the adiabatic nature of the process allows us to consider the distribution functions as equilibrium before dichotomous switching of the states and to use Parrondo's Lemma proved in [10]. A discrete (low-temperature) analogue of this Lemma, which describes the redistribution of the population probabilities of potential wells during adiabatic dichotomous fluctuations, was obtained in Ref. [11]. The general relations of the discrete analogue of Parrondo's lemma can be specified by substituting the minima and maxima of the hindered rotation potential, perturbed by dichotomous fluctuations of the electric field. This makes it possible to obtain analytical relations for the average velocity of the rotor directional rotation at arbitrary values of N and the parameter ε .

In Section 2, we derive the general equations for the average angular velocity of the hopping motion of a polar rotor in a periodic N -well potential of hindered rotation under the influence of adiabatic symmetric dichotomous fluctuations of an external electric field. From these formulas it follows that there is no ratchet effect in small terms of order ε^2 . A symmetry analysis of the hindered-rotation potential in the presence of the external electric field, as well as the symmetry analysis of the obtained general equations, is given in Section 3, where it is shown that the ratchet effect is absent for odd N as well as for the field directions coinciding with the axes of the wells and barriers. The properties of the ratchet effect for the case of even N are discussed in detail in Section 4. The main results of the paper are summarized in Section 5.

2. General relationships

Let us consider the process of adiabatic alternation of two spatially periodic potential reliefs with lifetimes τ^+ and τ^- , distinguished by the superscripts "+" and "-", which contain N wells and N barriers on their period L . The wells and barriers are located at nodes $x_n = (L/N)n$ and interstices $x_n + L/2N$, which are characterized by minima u_n^\pm and maxima v_n^\pm ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N$). Then, according to the results of Ref. [11], the average velocity of the hopping motion of a Brownian particle is determined as the ratio of the average displacement to one time cycle $\tau = \tau^+ + \tau^-$:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle v \rangle &= \frac{L}{\tau} \Lambda_N, \quad \Lambda_N = \sum_{n=2}^N Q_n \sum_{m=2}^n R_m, \\ Q_n &= Q_n^+ - Q_n^-, \quad R_m = R_m^+ - R_m^-, \\ Q_n^\pm &= \frac{\exp(\beta v_n^\pm)}{\sum_{m=1}^N \exp(\beta v_m^\pm)}, \quad R_m^\pm = \frac{\exp(-\beta u_m^\pm)}{\sum_{n=1}^N \exp(-\beta u_n^\pm)}, \\ \beta &= (k_B T)^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

For the rotational motion, x is an angular variable varying from 0 to 2π ($L = 2\pi$), and the average velocity $\langle v \rangle$ becomes the average angular velocity Ω . The potential of hindered rotation in "+" states, perturbed by a dichotomous change in the electric field, $\pm E$, oriented at an angle φ_E to the orientations of the minima of the unperturbed potential wells, has the form:

$$U^\pm(x) = \frac{1}{2} \Delta U (1 - \cos Nx) \mp \mu E \cos(x - \varphi_E). \quad (2)$$

The minimum and maximum values of the hindered-rotation potential are equal to 0 and ΔU at points $(2\pi/N)(n-1)$ and $(2\pi/N)(n-1/2)$, respectively. Therefore, at $\mu E \ll \Delta U$, the minima and maxima of the potential (2) are approximately equal to

$$\begin{aligned} u_n^\pm &= \mp \mu E \cos[(2\pi/N)(n-1) - \varphi_E], \\ v_n^\pm &= \Delta U \mp \mu E \cos[(2\pi/N)(n-1/2) - \varphi_E]. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Substituting Eqs. (3) into the expressions for R_m^\pm and Q_n^\pm from Eq. (1) yields

$$R_m^\pm = \frac{\exp\{\pm\varepsilon \cos[(2\pi/N)(m-1) - \varphi_E]\}}{\sum_{n=1}^N \exp\{\pm\varepsilon \cos[(2\pi/N)(n-1) - \varphi_E]\}},$$

$$Q_n^\pm = \frac{\exp\{\mp\varepsilon \cos[(2\pi/N)(n-1/2) - \varphi_E]\}}{\sum_{m=1}^N \exp\{\mp\varepsilon \cos[(2\pi/N)(m-1/2) - \varphi_E]\}} \quad (4)$$

where we introduced the dimensionless parameter $\varepsilon = \mu E/k_B T$.

Note, that the value of the hindered-rotation barrier ΔU is not included into the expression for Q_n^\pm and the average angular velocity Ω is then independent of it. This is a consequence of the dichotomy of the process and the adiabatic regime of motion, which is realized when the lifetimes of dichotomous states, τ^\pm , exceed the characteristic time for establishing equilibrium, w_0^{-1} , which can be estimated as $\nu^{-1} \exp(\beta\Delta U)$ (ν is the frequency of the impacts of a Brownian particle on the barriers). The larger ΔU , the much longer it takes to establish equilibrium and implement the adiabatic regime of motion. On the other hand, the fact that Ω does not depend on ΔU allows us to take ΔU so large that the inequality $\mu E \ll \Delta U$ holds true even for the sufficiently large strengths of the electric field. In this sense, the results (1)

and (4) are exact, and the parameter ε can be considered arbitrary.

For further analysis of the properties of the emerging ratchet effect, we note that $Q_n^\pm(\varphi_E) = R_n^\mp(\varphi_E - \pi/N)$. Therefore, the sought expressions for the average angular velocity Ω and the dimensionless parameter Λ_N will take on the form:

$$\Omega(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = \frac{2\pi}{\tau} \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E),$$

$$\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = -\sum_{n=2}^N R_n(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \sum_{m=2}^n R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E). \quad (5)$$

From the definitions (1) of the quantities R_m and R_m^\pm it follows that $\sum_{m=1}^N R_m = 0$. Using the explicit forms of the functions $R_m^\pm(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)$ from Eq. (4) yields

$$R_{m+N}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)$$

and

$$R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - 2\pi/N) = R_{m+1}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E).$$

These identities, with replacing the summation variables $n' = n+1$, $m' = m+1$, make it possible to show that the function (5) is periodic in the angular argument with period $2\pi/N$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - 2\pi/N) &= -\sum_{n=2}^N R_{n+1}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \sum_{m=2}^n R_{m+1}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = -\sum_{n'=3}^{N+1} R_{n'}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \\ &\times \sum_{m'=3}^{n'} R_{m'}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = -R_{N+1}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \left[\sum_{m'=2}^{N+1} R_{m'}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) - R_2(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \right] \\ &- \sum_{n'=2}^N R_{n'}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \left[\sum_{m'=2}^{n'} R_{m'}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) - R_2(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \right] \\ &= \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) + R_2(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \left[R_{N+1}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) + \sum_{n'=2}^N R_{n'}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \right] = \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E). \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

From the expression (5), the result of Ref. [8] follows, according to which, in the second order of the perturbation theory in ε , the ratchet effect is absent at $N > 2$, while, at $N = 2$, the ratchet effect is absent if the orientations of the electric field coincide with the orientations of the axes of the potential wells and barriers ($\varphi_E = 0, \pi/2$). Indeed, up to the terms of order ε^2 in the function $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)$, the denominators of quantities R_m^\pm and Q_n^\pm in Eq. (4) can be approximately set equal to N , and the exponential functions in the numerators of R_m^\pm and Q_n^\pm can be expanded into a Taylor series up to terms of order ε . This gives:

$$\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = -\frac{4\varepsilon^2}{N^2} \sum_{n=2}^N \cos[(2\pi/N)(n-1/2) - \varphi_E] \times \sum_{m=2}^n \cos[(2\pi/N)(m-1) - \varphi_E]. \quad (7)$$

Using the formula for geometric progression $\sum_{k=1}^N \alpha^k = \alpha(1 - \alpha^N)/(1 - \alpha)$, we get

$$\sum_{m=2}^n \cos[(2\pi/N)(m-1) - \varphi_E] = -\operatorname{Re} \frac{e^{-i\varphi_E}}{1 - e^{-2\pi i/N}} \left(1 - e^{2\pi i(n-1)/N}\right). \quad (8)$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) &= \frac{2\varepsilon^2}{N^2} \operatorname{Re} \frac{e^{-i\varphi_E}}{1 - e^{-2\pi i/N}} \sum_{n=2}^N \left[1 - e^{2\pi i(n-1)/N}\right] \left[e^{(2\pi i/N)(n-1/2) - i\varphi_E} + e^{-(2\pi i/N)(n-1/2) + i\varphi_E}\right] \\ &= \frac{2\varepsilon^2}{N^2} \operatorname{Re} \frac{1}{1 - e^{-2\pi i/N}} \left[e^{-2i\varphi_E + \pi i/N} \left(\sum_{n=2}^N e^{2\pi i(n-1)/N} - \sum_{n=2}^N e^{4\pi i(n-1)/N} \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + e^{-\pi i/N} \left(\sum_{n=2}^N e^{-2\pi i(n-1)/N} - N + 1 \right) \right] = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \delta_{N,2} \operatorname{Re} i e^{-2i\varphi_E} + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{N} \operatorname{Re} \frac{i}{\sin \pi/N} \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 \sin(2\varphi_E) \delta_{N,2}, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\delta_{n,m}$ is the Kronecker delta.

3. Symmetry properties

One of the necessary conditions for the existence of the ratchet effect is a certain asymmetry inherent to the system, specified by the potential energy of a Brownian particle. It is known that the ratchet effect is absent if

the potential energy is a symmetric or shift-symmetric periodic function of the coordinate [6, 12–15]:

$$\begin{aligned} U_s^\pm(x + x_s) &= U_s^\pm(-x + x_s), \\ U_{sh}^\pm(x + L/2) &= -U_{sh}^\pm(x), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where x_s is the coordinate of the symmetry axis. Using the expression (2) for the hindered-rotation potential, perturbed by the electric field, it is

easy to show that the symmetry condition (10) is satisfied at $x_s = \varphi_E = \pi q/N$, $q = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. For even and odd values of q , this is realized when the orientations of the electric field coincide with the directions of the minima and maxima of the potential wells and barriers, respectively. The shift-symmetry condition is realized for the odd values of N , $N = 2q + 1$. Let us demonstrate that the general expression (5) obtained above

satisfies the listed symmetry properties, i.e., that $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0) = \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \pi/N) = 0$ and $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = 0$ at $N = 2q + 1$.

When $\varphi_E = 0$, the quantities R_m^\pm and Q_n^\pm in Eq. (4) satisfy the equalities $R_{N+2-m}^\pm = R_m^\pm$ and $Q_{N+1-n}^\pm = Q_n^\pm$. Therefore, introducing new summation variables $m' = N + 2 - m$ and $n' = N + 1 - n$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0) &= \sum_{n=2}^N Q_n \sum_{m=2}^n R_m = \sum_{n'=1}^{N-1} Q_{n'} \sum_{m=2}^{N+1-n'} R_m = \sum_{n'=1}^{N-1} Q_{n'} \sum_{m'=n'+1}^N R_{m'} \\ &= \sum_{n'=1}^{N-1} Q_{n'} \left(\sum_{m'=1}^N R_{m'} - \sum_{m'=1}^{n'} R_{m'} \right) = - \sum_{n'=2}^N Q_{n'} \sum_{m'=1}^{n'} R_{m'} - Q_1 R_1 + Q_N \sum_{m'=1}^N R_{m'} \\ &= - \sum_{n'=2}^N Q_{n'} \sum_{m'=2}^{n'} R_{m'} - R_1 \left(\sum_{n'=2}^N Q_{n'} + Q_1 \right) = - \sum_{n'=2}^N Q_{n'} \sum_{m'=2}^{n'} R_{m'} = -\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0). \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Since $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0) = -\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0)$, we get $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0) = 0$, which is what needed to be proven.

The easiest way to prove the equality

$\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \pi/N) = 0$ is to use the property that follows from changing the summation order:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) &= - \sum_{n=2}^N R_n(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \sum_{m=2}^n R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = - \sum_{m=2}^N R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \sum_{n=m}^N R_n(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \\ &= - \sum_{m=2}^N R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \left[\sum_{n=1}^N R_n(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) - \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} R_n(\varepsilon, \varphi_E - \pi/N) \right] \\ &= \sum_{m=2}^N R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} R_{n+1}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E + \pi/N) = \sum_{m=2}^N R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \sum_{n=2}^m R_n(\varepsilon, \varphi_E + \pi/N) \\ &= -\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E + \pi/N). \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

In particular cases $\varphi_E = 0$ and π/N we have $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \pi/N) = -\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0)$, but since $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, 0) = 0$, then it equally be $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \pi/N) = 0$.

Let us move on to the proof of the equality

$\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = 0$ for odd values of N . First of all, we note that by virtue of the identity $\cos[(2\pi/N)(n-1) + \pi/N - \varphi_E] = -\cos[(2\pi/N)(n-1-r) - \varphi_E]$, the value $r = (N-1)/2$ entered here is an

integer for odd values of N . Therefore, if we denote by $\Sigma^\pm(\varphi_E)$ the denominator in R_n^\pm , then the identity $\Sigma^\pm(\varphi_E - \pi/N) = \Sigma^\mp(\varphi_E)$ holds. Therefore $R_n(\varphi_E - \pi/N) = R_{n-r}(\varphi_E)$ and the formula (5) takes on the following form:

$$\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = \sum_{n=2}^N R_{n-r}(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \sum_{m=2}^n R_m(\varepsilon, \varphi_E). \quad (13)$$

Taking into account the periodicity property $R_{n+N}^\pm = R_n^\pm$, we expand R_n and R_{n-r} (for the integer r) into a Fourier series

$$R_n = \sum_k \tilde{R}_k e^{ikn},$$

$$k = (2\pi/N)q, q = 0, \pm 1, \dots; N/2 < q \leq [N/2], \quad (14)$$

where $[x]$ denotes the integer part of a real number x . Here $\tilde{R}_{-k} = \tilde{R}_k^*$, since R_n is real and $\tilde{R}_0 = 0$ since $\sum_{n=1}^N R_n = 0$. Let us use the following result of nested summations

$$\sum_{n=2}^N e^{ikn} \sum_{m=2}^n e^{ik'm} = \frac{N}{1 - e^{ik}} \delta_{k+k', 0}, \quad (15)$$

valid for $k, k' \neq 0$. The formula (13) takes on the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) &= N \sum_{k \neq 0} \frac{e^{-ikr}}{1 - e^{ik}} \left| \tilde{R}_k \right| \\ &= \frac{N}{2} \sum_{k \neq 0} \left(\frac{e^{-ikr}}{1 - e^{ik}} + \frac{e^{ikr}}{1 - e^{-ik}} \right) \left| \tilde{R}_k \right| \\ &= \frac{N}{2} \sum_{k \neq 0} \frac{\sin k(r + 1/2)}{\sin(k/2)} \left| \tilde{R}_k \right| \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

From this result the equality $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = 0$ follows for odd values of N , since $\sin k(r + 1/2) = \sin \pi q = 0$ for any integer values of q .

4. Ratchet effect at even N

Relatively simple explicit analytical relationships for the average angular velocity of the ratchet effect can be obtained for small even values of the number of azimuthal potential wells. From Eq. (5) at $N = 2$ it immediately follows that

$$\Lambda_2(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = -\tanh(\varepsilon \sin \varphi_E) \tanh(\varepsilon \cos \varphi_E). \quad (17)$$

At $\varepsilon \ll 1$, the expression (17) reduces to the asymptotics (9). At $\varphi_E = 0$, the electric field changes the minima of the hindered-rotation potential, leaving the maxima unchanged, and at $\varphi_E = \pi/2$, on the contrary, it changes the maxima, leaving the minima unchanged (see the relations (3) at $N = 2$). The expression (17) shows that for the ratchet effect to exist, both maxima and minima must fluctuate simultaneously. This conclusion is consistent with the results of Ref. [8]. At $0 < \varphi_E < \pi/2$, the rotor moves counterclockwise, which corresponds to the rotation direction from the shallow well towards the low barrier (see Fig. 2 from Ref. [8]). Note that the kinetic description of the ratchet effect in a double-well potential with an arbitrary dependence of its minima and maxima on time was carried out in Ref. [16]. The presence of the inverse proportionality of the angular velocity to the period of the adiabatic process (see Eq. (5)) is a consequence of the instantaneous switching of the potential profiles (the time dependence of the electric field is described by a step function). If the electric field changes according to the law $E(t) = E_0 \cos \omega t$, then, at $\varepsilon \ll 1$, the angular velocity is determined by the following expression [8]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &\approx -\frac{\pi}{2} w_0 \varepsilon^2 \frac{\omega^2}{\omega^2 + 4w_0^2} \sin(2\varphi_E), \\ \omega &= \frac{2\pi}{\tau}, \quad w_0 = \nu \exp(-\beta \Delta U). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

In adiabatic mode, the average velocity $\Omega \approx -(\pi/8) w_0^{-1} \omega^2 \varepsilon^2 \sin(2\varphi_E)$ and is inversely

proportional to τ^2 , according to the analysis carried out in Ref. [16]. Moreover, if the process is not dichotomous, the result becomes dependent on the reorientation barrier ΔU .

At $N = 4$, in the expression (5) we should perform several summations and simplify the resulting terms. This yields the result

$$\Lambda_4(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = \frac{A(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)}{B(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)},$$

$$A(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = \sinh[\varepsilon \cos(\varphi_E - \pi/4)] [\sinh(\varepsilon \sin \varphi_E) - \sinh(\varepsilon \cos \varphi_E)] - \sinh[\varepsilon \sin(\varphi_E - \pi/4)] \times [\sinh(\varepsilon \sin \varphi_E) + \sinh(\varepsilon \cos \varphi_E)],$$

$$B(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) = \{\cosh[\varepsilon \cos(\varphi_E - \pi/4)] + \cosh[\varepsilon \sin(\varphi_E - \pi/4)]\} [\cosh(\varepsilon \sin \varphi_E) + \cosh(\varepsilon \cos \varphi_E)]. \quad (19)$$

The asymptotic behavior of small ε has the form:

$$\Lambda_4(\varepsilon, \varphi_E) \approx -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{48} \varepsilon^4 \sin(4\varphi_E). \quad (20)$$

Fig. 1 depicts a φ_E -family of functions $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)$ at $\varepsilon = 10$, corresponding to $N = 2, 4, 6, 8$. For $N = 2, 4$, the dependences were drawn using Eqs. (17) and (19), while, for $N = 6, 8$, using the general formula (5). In accordance with the results of Section 3, the zeros of the functions $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)$ occur at $\varphi_E = \pi q/N$, $q = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, while the maximum and minimum values of them occur at $\varphi_E = 2\pi(q - 1/4)/N$ and $\varphi_E = 2\pi(q + 1/4)/N$, respectively. By virtue of Eq. (12), the maximum and minimum values are related as $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, -\pi/(2N)) = -\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \pi/(2N))$. For a selected sufficiently large value $\varepsilon = 10$, the curves corresponding to $N = 2, 4$ have a flat dome shape, while the curves corresponding to $N = 6, 8$ are closer to a sinusoidal shape.

Figure 2 presents an ε -family of functions $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, \varphi_E)$ at $\varphi_E = -\pi/(2N)$, corresponding to $N = 2, 4, 6, 8$. Analysis of these dependencies shows that at $\varepsilon \ll 1$, the average angular velocity is proportional to $-\varepsilon^N \sin(N\varphi_E)$, which is in accordance with the asymptotic expressions (9) and (20). When $\varepsilon/N^2 \gg 1$, the value of $\Lambda_N(\varepsilon, -\pi/(2N))$ saturates to unity, which means that the average angular velocity tends to $2\pi/\tau$.

FIG. 1. Dependences of the average angular velocity (in units $2\pi/\tau$) on the angle of the orientation of the electric-field-strength vector to the axes of the wells of the hindered-rotation potential (the angle φ_E is measured in radians), calculated at $N = 2, 4, 6, 8$ (curves 1, 2, 3, 4, respectively). The ratio of the dipole rotor-electric field interaction energy to thermal energy (parameter ε) was chosen equal to 10.

5. Discussion and conclusion

This article analyzes in detail the mechanism of occurrence of the rotational ratchet effect of a polar rotor in an N -well potential of hindered rotation under the influence of adiabatic symmetric dichotomous fluctuations with a period τ of an external electric field. The analyses used the analytical relations of the discrete (low-temperature) analogue of Parrondo's lemma

FIG. 2. Dependence of the average angular velocity (in units $2\pi/\tau$) on the parameter ε at $\varphi_E = -\pi/(2N)$ and $N = 2, 4, 6, 8$ (curves 1, 2, 3, 4, respectively).

[11], which describes the redistribution of the probabilities of populations of potential wells during adiabatic dichotomous fluctuations. We obtained a general expression for the average angular velocity of the unidirectional discrete rotation, Ω , as a function of the direction φ_E of the applied field and the ratio of the interaction energy of the rotor with the electric field to the thermal energy, $\varepsilon = \mu E/k_B T$. Just as the translational ratchet effect is significantly restricted by the requirements imposed on the symmetry of the system, the rotational ratchet effect in an N -well potential of hindered rotation can exist only for odd N , as well as for field orientations φ_E different from the orientations of the axes of the wells and potential barriers with even N .

While, with quadratic accuracy in $\varepsilon \ll 1$,

the ratchet effect can exist only at $N = 2$, for sufficiently large values of ε , it exists for any even N . This regularity is well explained by the asymptotic behavior of the average angular velocity: $\Omega \propto \tau^{-1} \varepsilon^N \sin(N\varphi_E)$ for $\varepsilon \ll 1$ and $\Omega \rightarrow 2\pi/\tau$ for $\varepsilon/N^2 \gg 1$ and at $\varphi_E = -\pi/(2N)$.

In conclusion, we note that the discrete description of the jumping rotational motion used in this article, which gave fairly simple analytical relations for the average angular velocity, is valid at thermal energies much lower than the reorientation barrier ΔU of the hindered-rotation potential, which is a barrier of internal rotation and is sufficiently large for molecular systems. On the other hand, the adiabatic approximation used, justified for sufficiently large periods τ of changes in the electric field, leads to the fact that the results obtained do not depend on ΔU and are valid at thermal energies both lower ($\varepsilon \gg 1$) and higher ($\varepsilon \ll 1$) than the energy of interaction of the rotor with the electric field. Moreover, the discrete description makes it possible to simulate the characteristics of the rotary ratchet effect within the framework of the game theory [17].

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